
Formation of the Elements of Picture Literacy in Preschool Children

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Abstract: The article provides recommendations on the formation of elements of visual literacy in older preschool children, as well as creative development of preschool children in the process of visual activity.

Key words: visual literacy, visual activity, art, individual approach, artistic ability, childhood, crayon, watercolor, decoration, unusual image.

Introduction

In the "National Personnel Training Program" special attention is paid to the teaching of aesthetic subjects, in particular, in its "Principles of organization and development of continuous education" part, one of the principles of continuous education is education. is considered socialization. It is noted that it is necessary to create a rich aesthetic worldview in students, to form high spirituality, culture and creative thinking in them. Fine art has a wide opportunity to form these qualities in children. That is why it is possible to recognize as an important pedagogical problem the formation of certain worldviews, qualifications and skills in children before school education, in particular, the formation of visual literacy elements.

To arouse interest in the world around us, to realize oneself in it, to reflect a personal impression about something, to develop imagination and fantasy, to develop emotional sensitivity, to arouse in children the desire to see beauty in the world around them, to form an aesthetic attitude to the world in children it is necessary to develop visual activity from preschool children.

Art has always been an indicator of society's education and development, a criterion of its spiritual culture, and will remain so. We have been doing art since childhood. It surrounds us everywhere: architectural buildings, various household items, decorations, advertising, etc.

One of these types of art is fine art, the basics of which a person begins to understand from preschool age.

Discussion and Results

The development of the creative potential of a person should be carried out from early childhood, when the child begins to master various types of activities, including artistic activities, under the guidance of adults. There are great opportunities for the development of creativity in visual arts and, first of all, in drawing. Teaching a child to appreciate beauty in life and art correctly and correctly, to create it means enriching his inner world with such important qualities, without which a well-rounded person cannot and cannot exist. A person's path to the world of beauty and creativity begins with

family and kindergarten. Visual art is one of the important stages in the development of a child's creative abilities.

By using different techniques in children's art classes, it helps to develop the ability to see images in combinations of colored dots and lines and transform them into recognizable images. Children can acquire artistic techniques and interesting means of understanding the world around them by casually participating in the drawing process. The lesson becomes a creative process for the teacher and children with the help of various visual materials that go through the same stages as the artist's creative process. This activity plays the role of a source of fantasy and creativity. From a very young age, children try to reflect their impressions of the world around them in their visual creations through visual sensations. At the initial stage, they sometimes do not need paints, brushes and pencils. Children create images with their fingers, palms on the fogged glass, sticks on the sand, chalk on the asphalt, sometimes mother's neglected lipstick or paste on the mirror, spilled water on the table, buttons or beads from the grandmother's box. That is, everything that can leave a visible trace. At the same time, children not only reflect what they see and feel, but also get acquainted with materials and objects with different properties and qualities. As they grow older, preschool children first acquire the simplest skills and abilities of drawing using traditional methods and tools.

Over time, they meaningfully search for new ways to reflect the surrounding reality in their artistic creations. At that time, the teacher can make this work purposeful and introduce children to non-traditional techniques found in visual arts. It is necessary to add the most unusual visual aids to the educational process. For example: kerosene candle, comb, toothbrush, cotton bag, thread, etc. Conducting such activities helps to relieve children's fears, believe in their strengths, internal harmony with themselves and the world around them, and gives children new emotions that will be richer, fuller and brighter. I will teach you the topic of non-traditional drawing techniques, because it is interesting for both teachers and our children. All of them, without exception, quickly and willingly engage in group work, and after finishing it, they have a very emotional reaction to the result of their work - their drawings. Our children love to paint using techniques such as finger painting. Drawing in this non-traditional technique gives children great joy, they feel free and increase their self-esteem. They also love to stamp potatoes. Character printing allows children to prepare the objects of the world around them for after-life images, learn compositional drawing, and teach them to coordinate hand movements. This method of drawing a poke with a hard, semi-dry brush allows you to give the drawing the necessary expressiveness and realism, and the child will enjoy his work. The technique of drawing with wax pencils and watercolors is used to create the desired general tone or background of the picture, for example: sky, sand, water, etc. You can also use non-traditional drawing methods in your work: monotype, blotography, spray paint, scratch batik, etc.

We know that artistic talent manifests itself earlier than others. Children are talented in all types of art, but they have received the most permanent recognition in art, and it is not surprising, because the product of their work, drawings, can be preserved, displayed, studied as evidence of the talent of the young author.

Children have rich conditions for developing not only artistic, but also general creativity. The child has not yet built an impenetrable wall between "me" and "not me". He is ready to treat everything as if it were alive, to see the soul, character, desire - everything unique in any object and event. The child develops his own attitude, his own understanding of the subject, not without reason, even color for the baby is a means of expressing the attitude to the subject: dark, careless tones and lines - "bad, evil, scary" ; and vice versa, bright, light colors for beautiful, lovely, loving drawings. Gifted children often create "banal images", but the first one is distinguished not by describing "what", but by "how" and "why" they do it.

An individual approach to preschool children is necessary, if it is implemented in a certain system, it will have a positive effect on the formation of the personality of each child. It is necessary to study the manifestation of the child, to determine the reasons for the formation of the features of his character and behavior, to determine the appropriate tools and methods, to create clear organizational forms of implementing an individual approach to each child in general pedagogical work with all children.

Conclusion

Visual activities are especially interesting for children of preschool age, because they evoke a sense of joy, surprise, novelty and admiration for the world around them. All activities are aimed at developing creativity in preschool children, forming elements of visual literacy in them, creating ample opportunities to study children's characteristics and implement an individual approach to each child. This not only develops their artistic abilities, but also attention, observation, determination helps to develop talent and will. The formation of these qualities is an important condition for preparing a child for school and comprehensive development of a person.

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